

Assessment of some biochemical markers in electronic nicotine device smokers in Diyala province

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Abstract

Background: Vaping has gained significant popularity among young people in recent years as an alternative to conventional smoking. Despite being promoted as a safer substitute, the health consequences of vaping remain largely unknown. One area of concern is its impact on biochemical markers – substances that reflect changes in physiological processes. We hypothesized that identifying systemic indicators – such as proinflammatory and anti-inflammatory cytokines, vascular and growth factors, lipid mediators, and markers of elastin degradation – would provide insight into the potential toxicity of e-cigarette use.

This study sought to conduct an observational cross-sectional case-control analysis of several biochemical markers in the biological samples of e-cigarette users and non-smokers in Diyala Province, Iraq.

Methods: Plasma and urine samples were collected, and various biochemical markers were assessed in both e-cigarette users and non-users using the ELISA technique.

Results: Plasma levels of interleukin-6 (IL-6), interleukin-13 (IL-13), and the elastin degradation marker desmosine were significantly higher in e-cigarette users compared to non-smokers. In addition, a significant increase in plasma levels of vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) was observed in e-cigarette users compared to non-users. Furthermore, a moderate increase in urinary malonaldehyde levels – an indicator of lipid peroxidation – was noted in e-cigarette users.

Conclusion: This study highlights significant biochemical alterations in e-cigarette users compared to non-smokers. Elevated levels of inflammatory markers (IL-6 and IL-13) and desmosine suggest an inflammatory response and potential lung tissue degradation associated with vaping. Oxidative stress markers, such as malonaldehyde, did not show significant differences between the groups. These findings suggest that e-cigarette use may contribute to inflammation and extracellular matrix degradation, raising concerns about its long-term health effects. Further research with larger cohorts and longitudinal studies is essential to clarify the systemic impact of vaping.

Keywords

electronic cigarettes, toxicity, marker, vaping, inflammation

Introduction

TElectronic cigarettes (e-cigarettes) are battery-powered devices that produce inhalable aerosols, such as vapor or smoke (Jackson et al. 2025). This vapor is produced by heating the e-liquid combination contained within the e-cigarette. E-cigarette juice comprises propylene glycol, vegetable glycerin, nicotine in varying quantities, flavoring ingredients, and other chemical substances (Klosterhalfen et al. 2025). Nicotine itself carries many risks. It has been scientifically proven that although e-cigarettes contain fewer impurities and lower levels of tar and related substances, they still expose the body to elevated liver enzyme levels, drug interactions, and other health risks (Ibrahim et al. 2024). Recently, a range of additives such as terpenes, mineral oil, chemical compounds, and contaminated substances have been included in e-cigarette juices and various vaping products (Jankowski et al. 2024). Electronic nicotine devices (ENDs) are packed with an abundance of ingredients that are not naturally found in a regular cigarette (Yingst et al. 2024). The following are just a few of the chemicals that often make up the various components of these devices. Among these components is an array of flavoring chemicals. Some produce airway epithelial cell-specific toxicity, similar to that observed in the airways of cigarette smokers and patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (Yingst et al. 2024). The humectants, such as propylene glycol and vegetable glycerin, are known to generate both toxic aldehydes and potential carcinogenic carbonyl compounds. Even though polyethylene glycol is relatively safe for health and is used to treat infections and hepatic encephalopathy, many studies have shown some risks and side effects in humans (Gnanasekar and Veluswamy 2024). Formaldehyde, acetaldehyde, and acrolein are found in large amounts in END aerosols. There are also volatile organic compounds (VOCs) that make up the base of the e-liquid. These compounds have detrimental effects on human respiratory defense mechanisms.

Flavoring chemicals present in e-cigarette liquid, such as diacetyl (2,3-butanedione) and 2,3-pentanedione, have been associated with bronchiolitis obliterans syndrome (Faeq et al. 2024). Additionally, there are a variety of toxic heavy metals. Many of these are present in the vapor produced by the metal coil used to heat and aerosolize the e-liquid (Granata et al. 2024). There is also an overabundance of unique flavoring aldehydes and diketones in these devices. Moreover, during the formation process of various e-liquids or e-cig aerosols, aldehydes, which are known lung irritants, are produced. In terms of carcinogens, studies have concluded that these devices produce similar levels of formaldehyde-releasing agents as found in traditional cigarette smoke. It was also found that nicotine degrades into chemicals that may form cancer-causing organic nitrosamines and other toxic and carcinogenic chemicals. Furthermore, END use generates nicotine butyrate, a chemical that has been identified as exhibiting a reduced cigarette kick while still

possibly maintaining an addiction factor due to ease of inhalation, smoothness of vapor, and an increase in pH levels (Yingst et al. 2024).

Electronic cigarettes have recently gained popularity in Iraq as well as globally. Regardless of the belief among e-cigarette users that vaping is less hazardous than smoking traditional cigarettes, several epidemiological studies indicate otherwise (Faeq et al. 2024). A previous study demonstrated that e-cigarette consumption can modify vital parameters, such as heart rate and blood pressure, affecting the cardiovascular system in users (Salman 2019; Ghanim et al. 2024). Recent studies have highlighted a complex interplay between metabolic disorders, lifestyle factors, and carcinogenesis. Smoking causes genetic alteration and type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), which is characterized by chronic low-grade inflammation, insulin resistance, and hyperglycemia (Salman et al. 2023a).

Further research in this domain will provide more precise evaluations of the health concerns linked to vaping compared to smoking and will support clinical and regulatory determinations. Because of the novelty of e-cigarettes, there is a dearth of validated exposure biomarkers that enable researchers and physicians to precisely identify and quantify e-cigarette consumption, as well as to distinguish it from traditional tobacco products (Alwan et al. 2024).

Biomarkers of toxicity are molecules employed to evaluate the biochemical, physiological, and other measurable effects of exposure to a specific toxin (Devi et al. 2024).

Interleukin-6 (IL-6)

IL-6 is a cytokine that has multifaceted effects. It is primarily synthesized by monocytes and macrophages, and its biological roles include lymphocyte activation, the initiation of inflammatory processes, angiogenesis, and stimulation of acute phase protein synthesis and fever (Devi et al. 2024; Paranga et al. 2024).

Numerous studies indicate that smokers have increased IL-6 concentrations in their blood relative to non-smokers. Nevertheless, several research teams indicate that blood IL-6 levels are comparable between smokers and non-smokers (Al-tameemi et al. 2022). Plasma investigations demonstrate that elevated IL-6 concentrations are present in cigarette smokers relative to non-smokers (Beegam et al. 2024; Stephan et al. 2024; Śniadach et al. 2025). By contrast, Al-tameemi et al.'s research found no association between IL-6 levels and smoking intensity (Al-tameemi et al. 2022). Most research on saliva testing revealed no significant changes in IL-6 concentrations between smokers and non-smokers (Alsaifi and Farhan 2019; Qiu et al. 2024). In e-cigarette users, irrespective of the substance examined, IL-6 levels are increased compared to non-smokers. Elevated levels of IL-6 are seen in the plasma, saliva, and urine of e-cigarette users (Al-Hussani et al. 2023; Boss et al. 2024). Some studies show that e-cigarettes do not affect IL-6 levels (Allbright et al. 2024).

Interleukin-13 (IL-13)

This cytokine is primarily involved in immune responses, particularly in allergic inflammation and asthma. It plays a crucial role in airway remodeling, mucus hypersecretion, and eosinophilic inflammation. IL-13 is produced by various immune cells, including T-helper 2 (Th2) cells, and is a key mediator in conditions such as asthma, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), and other respiratory diseases (Zwoliński et al. 2024). E-cigarette exposure may influence IL-13 expression, leading to airway inflammation, mucus hypersecretion, and potential fibrosis. However, more research is needed to fully understand the long-term effects (Kirkham et al. 2024).

Other indicators of oxidative stress, such as malonaldehyde (MDA), were also influenced by conventional smoking; however, there is a paucity of research on this aspect with regard to e-cigarette smoking (Mohammed et al. 2018). Meanwhile, superoxide dismutase (SOD) levels were diminished, signifying increased oxidative stress and compromised antioxidant defense mechanisms, which can affect cells at the cellular level and potentially lead to cancers such as lung or breast cancer (Ebersole et al. 2020; Mohammed et al. 2021).

This study was designed as an observational case-control study analyzing various biomarkers in blood and urine samples of e-cigarette users and non-smokers in Diyala Province.

Methods and subjects

Participants and procedure

The current study was done at the College of Medicine, University of Diyala. Participants were recruited from various locations across the province between November 2024 and January 2025. Blood samples were collected to obtain plasma and to determine various biomarkers, including IL-6, IL-13, VEGF, and desmosine levels. In addition, malonaldehyde levels were measured in urine. Plasma and urine biomarker levels were quantified using commonly accessible ELISA kits. A previously designated questionnaire was used for demographic data collection. All research participants provided informed consent, and the study was reviewed and approved by the Scientific and Ethical Committees at the College of Medicine, University of Diyala, Iraq (code no. 2025ODS897).

Inclusion criteria

Participants were recruited based on the following criteria:

Age Range: Volunteers aged 20 to 35 years were included. **E-cigarette users:** Individuals who had been using e-cigarettes exclusively for at least six months, with a frequency of at least one session per day.

Non-smokers: Individuals who had never used e-cigarettes or any other tobacco products.

Health Status: Participants were required to be generally healthy, with no history of chronic illnesses.

Medication Use: Volunteers should not be taking anti-inflammatory medications, corticosteroids, or any medication that could influence inflammatory or oxidative stress markers, as these medications alter interleukin levels.

Respiratory Health: Participants must not have had a current or recent (within three months) history of respiratory infections or conditions such as asthma or chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). **Consent:** All participants provided written informed consent before enrollment in the study.

Exclusion criteria

Participants were excluded from the study if they met any of the following criteria: **Mixed or Dual Smokers:** Individuals who used both e-cigarettes and traditional cigarettes or other nicotine-containing products.

History of Chronic Diseases: Participants with a history of lung diseases (COPD, asthma), cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, or cancer were excluded.

Recent Illness or Infection: Volunteers with an active infection, recent flu, fever, or inflammatory disease were not included.

Use of Certain Medications: Individuals taking anti-inflammatory drugs, corticosteroids, or immunosuppressants were excluded to prevent confounding effects.

Pregnancy or Lactation: Female participants who were pregnant or lactating were not included in the study.

Study design

An observational case-control study was conducted to examine several biochemical markers in the plasma and urine samples of e-cigarette users and non-smokers. Biological specimens, including plasma and urine, were acquired. Venous blood (5–10 mL) was drawn, and the plasma samples were promptly kept at -40°C until analysis. Participants' urine samples (25–30 mL) were separated and stored in a freezer at -18°C until analysis. Participants were categorized into two groups: non-users (number = 50) and e-cigarette users (number = 55).

Reagents and kits

Kits were used for detecting interleukin-6 (IL-6) (CSB-E04638h, Cusabio), interleukin-13 (IL-13) (CSB-E04601h, Cusabio), vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) (CSB-E11718h, Cusabio), desmosine (an elastin degradation marker) (CSB-E12871h, Cusabio), and malonaldehyde (a lipid mediator and marker of oxidative stress) (CSB-E13877h, Cusabio).

Chemicals for sample preparation: Phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) for washing steps during ELISA, standard diluents, and control reagents provided with the ELISA kits.

ELISA reader (Biobase, China): for measuring absorbance and quantifying biomarker levels.

Pipettes and Microplates: For handling and transferring samples during the ELISA procedure.

Participants' information collection

Questionnaire: This was designed for collecting demographic data and smoking habits.

Results

The baseline demographic and e-cigarette vaping status factors assessed in the laboratory using the ELISA method are given below (Table 1).

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of e-smokers and non-smokers.

Subjects	E-smoker (mean \pm SD)	Non-smoker (mean \pm SD)
Number	55	50
Age (years)	21.8 \pm	22.1 \pm
BMI (kg.m ⁻²)	25.2 \pm 2.2	24.8 \pm 3.1
Smoking duration (years)	2.00 \pm 1.64	-
Smoking time (min)	7.75 \pm 3.14	-
Smoking cessation (min)	8.79 \pm 5.50	-

The study included 55 adult male e-cigarette users and 55 healthy non-smoker volunteers. The mean age of e-cigarette users between 20 and 35 was similar to that of non-smokers (22–35). E-cigarette users had an average vaping duration of 2.00 \pm 1.64 years, with a frequency of 7.75 \pm 3.14 sessions per day, each lasting around 8.79 \pm 5.50 minutes.

Plasma interleukin-6 was used as a marker of inflammation, with significantly higher levels in the e-cigarette users group compared to the non-smokers group. Specifically, IL-6 levels in e-cigarette smokers were 7.8115 \pm 1.06 pg/mL, compared to 3.158 \pm 0.0147 pg/mL in non-smokers, with a highly significant p-value of 0.000051. Similarly, interleukin-13 (IL-13) showed a marked increase in e-cigarette smokers (8.55 \pm 0.64 pg/mL) versus non-smokers (4.92 \pm 0.29 pg/mL), with a p-value of 0.00001.

Desmosine, a biomarker of elastin degradation, was notably elevated in e-cigarette smokers (0.1025 \pm 0.01 μ g/mL) compared to non-smokers (0.004 \pm 0.0015 μ g/mL), also with a p-value of 0.00001, indicating potential lung tissue damage associated with e-cigarette use.

On the other hand, malonaldehyde (MDA), a marker of oxidative stress, showed no statistically significant difference between e-cigarette smokers (118.65 \pm 23.8 nmol/mL) and non-smokers (112 \pm 21.7 nmol/mL), with a p-value of 0.418847.

Lastly, vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), a key regulator of angiogenesis, was slightly higher in e-cigarette smokers (37.7 \pm 5 pg/mL) compared to non-smokers (28.9 \pm 2.65 pg/mL), but this difference was not statistically significant (p-value = 0.06424).

These findings indicate that e-cigarette use is associated with increased inflammatory cytokines (IL-6 and IL-13) and higher desmosine levels suggestive of lung matrix degradation, while oxidative stress and angiogenic markers did not show significant differences between the groups (Table 2, Fig. 1).

Discussion

This study investigates the potential health effects of e-cigarette usage by comparing biomarkers in e-cigarette users and non-smokers. There is an increased inflammation, as elevated levels of both proinflammatory (IL-6) (Świątkowska et al. 2024) and anti-inflammatory (IL-13) cytokines in e-cigarette users suggest a complex inflammatory response. An increase in proinflammatory IL-6 levels and anti-inflammatory IL-13 levels could indicate that e-cigarette use may trigger an inflammatory process in the body. This response aligns with a previously published article reporting that IL-6 levels were significantly higher (P < 0.01) among cigarette and waterpipe smokers than e-cigarette users and non-smokers (Moqueem et al. 2018). Numerous inflammatory illnesses, such as lung fibrosis, asthma, allergies, and cancer, are influenced by IL-13 (Crotty Alexander et al. 2015; Al-Hussaini 2023; Al-Hussaini and Al-Zobaidy 2024).

Higher desmosine levels suggest an increased breakdown of the extracellular matrix, which is crucial for tissue integrity. This indicates a potential risk for tissue damage, which could have implications for various organs and systems. Plasma desmosine functions as an indicator of elastin breakdown and is associated with increased cardiovascular risk and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) (Cantor 2023). Chronic cigarette smoking induces elastin degradation in the alveolar wall through proteolytic activity, resulting in emphysema, increased cardiovascular risk, and COPD. In our research, this biomarker – typically linked to emphysema – was detected for the first time in the context of e-cigarette use. This result indicates that e-cigarettes may cause pulmonary emphysema (Cantor 2023; Kidane et al. 2024; Świątkowska et al. 2024).

The systemic nature of these alterations can also be reflected in hepatic and muscular physiology. A previous study conducted in Iraq highlighted the significant correlation between nutritional status and muscle strength in liver cirrhosis patients, emphasizing how chronic systemic insults can affect musculoskeletal performance. Similarly, chronic inhalation of nicotine salts might exacerbate muscular weakness and nutritional deficiencies via pro-inflammatory mediators and appetite-regulatory pathways.

Regarding vascular effects, increased VEGF levels may indicate enhanced vascular growth, which could have both positive and negative consequences depending on the context (Salman et al. 2023b). In this study, significantly increased VEGF levels may reflect systemic consequences of compensatory responses to other pro-inflammatory mediators. However, studies have shown that cigarette smoke alters VEGF levels. Moreover, evidence of

Table 2. Comparison of the means of different biomarkers in e-smokers and non-smokers.

Parameter	E-cigarette smoker (mean ± SE)	Non-smoker (mean ± SE)	P value
IL-6	7.8115 ± 1.06	3.158 ± 0.0147	0.000051
IL-13	8.55 ± 0.64	4.92 ± 0.29	0.00001
Desmosine	0.1025 ± 0.01	0.004 ± 0.0015	0.00001
Malonaldehyde	118.65 ± 23.8	112 ± 21.7	0.418847
VEGF	37.7 ± 5	28.9 ± 2.65	0.06424

Figure 1. Plasma and urine biomarkers in an e-smokers group compared with the non-smokers group.

oxidative stress was limited; the absence of a significant difference in malonaldehyde levels suggests that oxidative stress may not be a major contributor to the health effects observed in this study. Our findings build upon previously published studies on nicotine salt aerosol, which is associated with the production of reactive species similar to those generated by the Fenton reaction – primarily hydroxyl (OH) radicals and other reactive oxygen species (ROS) (Tran et al. 2024).

Conclusion

This study highlights significant biochemical alterations in e-cigarette smokers compared to non-smokers. Elevated levels of inflammatory markers (IL-6 and IL-13) and desmosine suggest an inflammatory response and potential lung tissue degradation associated with vaping. Additionally, a non-significant increase in VEGF levels may suggest possible vascular alterations. Oxidative stress markers, such as malonaldehyde, did not show significant differences between the groups. These findings suggest that e-cigarette use may contribute to inflammatory processes and extracellular matrix degradation, raising concerns about its long-term health effects. Further research, including larger cohorts and longitudinal studies, is essential to clarify the systemic impact of vaping.

Limitation of the study

This study has many limitations, including a male-only sample: The findings may not be generalizable to female

e-cigarette users. In addition, larger sample sizes are needed to increase the generalizability of the findings. Furthermore, with limited biomarkers assessed, a more comprehensive assessment of health effects would require a broader range of biomarkers.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

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Author contributions

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

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Supplementary material 1

Biomarkers of electronic nicotine delivery systems (ENDS) use

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